

Research article

The distribution of diphthongs in Northern and Southern dialects of Vietnamese

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Abstract: This study aims to show the geographical distribution of so-called “diphthongs” in Vietnamese dialects for the purpose of analyzing and rethinking their status in the syllable structure of the Northern and the Southern dialects. It also shows that other phenomena concerning vowel sequences in both dialects are distributed almost the same way as diphthongs. The findings support the close relationship of these phenomena, especially in the Southern dialect, and they concern the preference for heavy syllables in the Southern dialect.*

Keywords: Vietnamese; diphthongs; Southern dialect

1. Introduction

In the inventory of Northern Vietnamese (NV) vowel phonemes, three vowels, /ie uɯ uo/, are commonly labeled ‘diphthong’ (Đoàn 1977, Nguyen 1997). The same phonemes whose phonetic realization is slightly different are also distinguished in the Southern Vietnamese (SV) (see Table 1).

Table 1 Vowel phonemes in NV and SV¹

NV			SV		
ie	ɯɣ	uo	iə	ɯə	uə
i	ɯ	u	i	ɨ/ɯ	u
e	ɣ	o	e	ɣ	o
ɛ	ʌ	ɔ	ɛ	ʌ	ɔ
a	ɐ		a	ɐ	

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¹ Data pertaining to the Northern dialect were provided by the female consultant (ID number: HN16) who was born in Nam Định province in 1990 and that of Southern dialect were provided by the female consultant (ID number: SG05) who was born in Tiền Giang province in 1989.

Emerich (2021) disputed about their status in the syllable structure of the Hanoi dialect and suggested they should be grouped with eleven other monophthongs, /a ɛ ʌ ɤ ɯ ɛ e i ɔ o u/, based on their similarities in phonetic and phonological behaviors. She conclusively called them ‘contour vowels’ to distinguish them from the true diphthongs that consist of ten vowel-/j/-glide diphthongs, /aj ɛj ʌj ɔj oj ɤj ɯj uj ɯɤj uoj/, and nine vowel-/w/-glide diphthongs, /aw ɛw ʌw ɛw ew iw ɯw iew ɯɤw/. In this study, we continue to use the term ‘diphthong’ for the three phonemes so that readers can easily determine the objective of this study.

Pham (2006) pointed out that in the Saigon dialect these three phonemes are diphthongs in final position, while in closed syllables long high vowels [i:], [ɛ:] and [u:] correspond to the three diphthongs in the Hanoi dialect. Pham’s description is a phonetic one and those three long high vowels correspond to /i/, /u/ and /u/ in this study. Accordingly, my data on correspondence match that of Pham’s and support her assertion.

Table 2 Diphthongs in closed and open syllables

	Orthography	NV	SV	
(a)	<i>tiêm</i>	tiem ¹	tim ¹	‘to inject’
	<i>tuôm</i>	tuɯm ¹	tum ¹	‘to emit’
	<i>buôm</i>	buom ²	bum ²	‘sail’
	<i>tiền</i>	tien ²	tiŋ ²	‘money’
	<i>lươn</i>	luɯŋ ¹	luŋ ¹	‘eel’
	<i>cuôn</i>	kuon ⁵	kuŋ ⁵	‘to roll’
	<i>tiếng</i>	tiɛŋ ⁵	tiŋ ⁵	‘voice’
	<i>thương</i>	t ^h ɯɤŋ ¹	t ^h ɯŋ ¹	‘injured’
<i>uống</i>	ʔuon ⁵	ʔuŋ ⁵	‘to drink’	
(b)	<i>tia</i>	tiɛ ¹	tiə ¹	‘ray’
	<i>tua</i>	tuɯ ¹	tuə ¹	‘fur’
	<i>tua</i>	tuo ¹	tuə ¹	‘fringe’

Fig. 1 shows the distribution of the correspondence illustrated in (a) of Table 1, and Fig. 2 shows that of (b) of Table 1. The isogloss between where (a) is present and where it is not is placed at Hải Vân Pass locates between Thừa Thiên Huế province and Đà Nẵng City. This place is also regarded as the border separating the Northern and Southern dialects of Vietnamese (Hoàng 2004). The correspondence of (b) distributes over almost the entire country, except for the case of a consultant from Ninh Thuận province (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 *tia* (tia^1 :⊙, ti^1 :◆)

The purpose of this study is to point out other phenomena that are closely related to the correspondence (a) and contribute to the project of clarifying the underlying rules that differentiate the surface phonemic structures of Northern and Southern dialects of Vietnamese.

2. Occurrence of glides

Concerning the difference in phonetic values of vowels, another phenomenon is the germination of glides between initials and high vowels in the open syllables of SV. Their actual realization is illustrated in Table 3, and their geographical distribution is shown in Fig. 3-5.

Table 3 Occurrence of glides in SV (1)

Orthography	(a)	(b)	
<i>ti</i>	[ti:ʔ]	[tʃi:ʔ]	'service'
<i>tu</i>	[tu:ʔ]	[tʃtu:ʔ]	'private'
<i>tu</i>	[tu:ʔ]	[tʃu:ʔ]	'to practice'

Fig. 3 *ti* ([ti:ɿ]:◆, [tʰi:ɿ]:○)

Fig. 4 *tu* ([tu:ɿ]:◆, [tʰu:ɿ]:○)

Fig. 5 *tu* ([tu:ɿ]:◆, [tʰu:ɿ]:○)

Here again, the isogloss between (a) and (b) is located at the same place as the case shown in Table 1 (a); that is, Hải Vân Pass.

Another case of the glide insertion that occurs in the coda position after the high-mid vowels /e ɤ o/ is observed in a limited region of SV. The phenomenon is illustrated in Table 4.

Table 4 Occurrence of glides in SV (2)

Orthography	(a)	(b)	
<i>tê</i>	[te:ɿ]	[te'ɿɿ]	'to be numbed'
<i>tơ</i>	[tɤ:ɿ]	[tɤ'ɿ'ɿ]	'silk'
<i>tô</i>	[to:ɿ]	[to'ũɿ]	'bowl'

The geographical distribution of (b) extends from Bình Thuận province southward, as shown in Fig. 6-8.

3. Vowel correspondence in /j/-coda and /w/-coda syllables

Concerning diphthongs (in the sense meant by both Emerich and I), other phenomena are observed in /j/-final and /w/-final syllables. The rhymes in question are written *ây*, *ay*, *ai*, *âu*, *au*, and *ao* in orthography. Their phonetic realization is shown in Table 5. Their geographical distribution is not as straightforward as that in Fig. 2-4, but the general tendency is that (a) forms are dominant in NV and (b) forms are dominant in SV. The third form is only found in Quảng Nam province, as we can see in Fig. 9-14.

Fig.6. *tê* ([te:1]:◆, [te:ĩ]:◎)Fig.7. *tơ* ([tx:1]:◆, [tx:õ]:◎)Fig.8. *tô* ([to:1]:◆, [to:ũ]:◎)

Table 5 Rhyme correspondence in /j/-final and /w/-final syllables

Orthography	(a)	(b)	Quảng Nam	
<i>cây</i>	kaj ¹	kɛj ¹	kɛj ¹	‘tree’
<i>cay</i>	kɛj ¹	kaj ¹	ka ¹	‘spicy’
<i>cái</i>	kaj ⁵	kaj ⁵	kəa ⁵	‘female’
<i>cầu</i>	kaw ²	kɛw ²	kɛw ²	‘bridge’
<i>sáu</i>	sɛw ⁵	saw ⁵	sa ⁵	‘six’
<i>sao</i>	saw ¹	saw ¹	so ¹	‘star’

In the (b)-type dialects, the syllables with orthographic *ay* vs. *ai* and *au* vs. *ao* are phonemically identical to /aj/ and /aw/, respectively. However, in the same dialects, the syllables with orthographic *ây* vs. *ay/ai* and *âu* vs. *aulao* are phonemically distinguished: /ɛj/ vs. /aj/ and /ɛw/ vs. /aw/. In the cases of *ây* vs. *ay* and *âu* vs. *au*, the phonetic realizations are especially different between (a)-type dialects and (b)-type dialects: /ɛj/ vs. /aj/ and /ɛw/ vs. /aw/ in (a)-type, and /ɛj/ and /aj/ and /ɛw/ and /aw/ in (b)-type. The Quảng Nam forms are unique and need a separate analysis.

It is obvious that (a) forms are dominant in NV. Meanwhile, (b) forms are mainly distributed in the SV region, but the distribution is split into two sub-regions—the Quảng Nam-Quảng Ngãi and Mekong Delta sub-regions. Historically speaking, the SV dialectal region emerged after the 15th century, and the region between the Quảng Nam-Quảng Ngãi and Mekong Delta sub-regions lies Hochiminh City, which is the center of Vietnam’s economy and commerce. This situation can be classified as an ABA distribution in which the A-form is older than the B-form is. In the SV region, (b) forms are regarded as original, whereas (a) forms observed in Hochiminh City and

shared by the NV region can be regarded as newer. As a result, (a) forms are regarded as NV forms and (b) forms as SV forms.

Fig.9. *cây*
(kaj1: ◐, kɛj1: ○)

Fig.10. *cay*
(kɛj1: ○, kaj1: ●, ka1: ★)

Fig.11. *cái*
(kaj5: ●, kɛa5: ★)

Fig.12. *càu*
(kaw2: ◐, kɛw2: ○)

Fig.13. *sáu*
(sɛw5: ○, ɟaw5: ●, ɟa5: ★)

Fig.14. *sao*
(saw1, ɟaw1: ●, ɟo1: ★)

4. Interpretation of the geographical distribution

The geographical distributions of Table 2 (a), Table 3 (b) and Table 5(b) are essentially the same, and their common isogloss lies at Hải Vân Pass. The location has been traditionally regarded as the border separating NV and SV. On the other hand, the isogloss of Table 4 (a)-(b) is located at the border between Ninh Thuận and Bình Thuận provinces. It is also the border of initial v [v] and v [w~j] (Shimizu 2016). The isoglosses along these borders are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6 Isoglosses of phenomena in this study and Shimizu (2016)

Isoglosses	Phenomena in this study	Shimizu (2016)
(1) Hải Vân Pass	Table 2 (a), Table 3 (b), Table 5(b)	
(2) Ninh Thuận~Bình Thuận	Table 4	v [v] ~ v [w/j]

To interpret the co-relation among the phenomena introduced so far, let us first summarize the diachronic aspects of SV development. Immigrants to the Southern region are generally from Northern or Central Vietnam. It was not until the end of the 17th century that they reached the region of modern Saigon (Gia Định, at that time). Fortunately, some Romanized Catholic documents dating from the 17th century are available. One of the most famous ones is Alexandre de Rhodes' *Dictionarium Annamiticum Lusitanum, et Latinum* which has a hybrid nature. The rhyme system with nasal and stop codas in *Dictionarium* is similar to that of the present Northern system, and different from that of present SV. Therefore, the present Northern system can be regarded as the origin of the present Southern (Saigon) system. In this sense, the NV phonemic system is regarded as the input of the SV development process.

Here I claim the preference for heavy syllable in SV. Table 2 (a) shows the general tendency of SV to monophthongize the NV diphthongs. This process does not influence the syllable weight in closed syllables: CVC > CVC. However, when they appear in the open syllable, they remain diphthongs to generate a heavy syllable of a new type with the second elements of diphthongs reinterpreted as codas. The analysis leading to the identification of the second elements of diphthongs as codas in SV was also proposed by Pham (2006). This analysis allows the interpretation of the phonemic process from NV input to SV output: CV > CVV.

The occurrence of glides in the case shown in Table 3 can also be interpreted in terms of the preference for heavy syllable in SV. This phenomenon is applicable only to the three high vowels /i u u/. The process is phonetically interpreted as CV > CVV. On the other hand, the phenomenon in Table 4 can be interpreted as a process of diphthongization occurring in the rhymes with high-mid vowels /e ɤ o/ as well.

However, its geographical distribution in SV is more limited than is the case in Table 3.

In both the phonemic and phonetic processes, the result of the occurrence of glides [ɿi] and [ɿu] in SV (Table 3) is phonetically quite close to the input /ʌj/ and /ʌw/ of NV. I suppose this situation caused the avoidance of the merger of rhymes spelled *i* vs. *ây* and *u* vs. *âu*, respectively. Here, I claim that the vowel correspondence introduced in Table 5 can be interpreted as the result of avoidance of the merger. The avoidance of the merger caused the following changes in SV: ʌj > ɐj; ɐj > aj and ʌw > ɐw; ɐw > aw. In other words, the vowel shift ʌ > ɐ > a occurred in the rhymes with /j/ and /w/ codas. However, the last process ɐ > a in /j/- and /w/-coda syllables contradictorily results in the merger of orthographic *ay* vs. *ai* and *au* vs. *ao* rhymes, realized phonemically as /aj/ and /aw/, respectively. This merger is commonly observed even in Hochiminh City where the forms /kɛj¹/ (*cây*) and /kɛw²/ (*câu*) in Table 5 are not observed in the data.

4. Conclusion

This study observed the geographical distribution of so-called diphthongs in NV and SV. Most of the phenomena concerning the vowel sequences that structure the phonemic and phonetic diphthongs in Vietnamese are observed in the region traditionally regarded as the SV region. Asserting the NV rhyme system is an input to the SV development process, I pointed out the preference for heavy syllable in SV to account for the phonemic and phonetic processes concerning diphthongs. To reinforce this claim, the following further tasks are necessary.

First, it is necessary to make clear the relationship between syllable types—light or heavy—and tones. According to my auditory impression, the occurrence of glides in Table 3 and Table 4 may slightly differ depending on tones. The data in this study do not cover all the patterns of segmental sequences with tones, which is information that is most needed.

Second, the different behavior of /w/-glide in NV and SV is another important issue that concerns the syllable type in SV. Hoàng (2004) argued that SV generally lacks the /w/-glide in its syllable structure, which caused the process in SV: /xwɛ³/ > /ɛ³/ (*khỏe* ‘to be healthy’). This process seems contradictory to the heavy syllable hypothesis in SV proposed in this study and needs further analysis from phonemic and phonetic points of view.

Third, the different outputs among the different generations of SV speakers should also be considered. As Shimizu (2016) pointed out, the phonetic realization of the initial consonant spelled *v* differs depending on the generation. The geographical distribution of phonetic realization of syllables in Table 5 by different generations will be an especially important issue.

Given each issue mentioned above, the heavy syllable hypothesis of SV would be one of the typological features of SV compared with those of NV.

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